

HOTEL ECONOMY IN COMPARISON WITH UZBEKISTAN AND TURKEY

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Annotation: *This article provides information on the establishment of the Uzbek-Turkish Lyceum of Hospitality and Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan, agreements between Uzbekistan and Turkey, the use of Turkish experience in the construction of new hotels in Uzbekistan. Proposals of the National Company "Uzbektourism" and the Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Turkey. Production of students studying in the field of tourism and the organization of internships abroad.*

Keywords: *tourism, hotel industry, Uzbek-Turkish lyceum of tourism and hotel management, Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Turkey, National Company "Uzbektourism"*

INTRODUCTION

In order to further improve tourism and the hotel industry in Uzbekistan, various new decisions and agreements have been signed with foreign countries, including Turkey, over the years. According to a statement issued by the State Committee for Tourism Development of Uzbekistan, from 2018 to 2022 it is planned to build 278 hotels in the country. The experience of the Turkish state is being used in the construction of hotels. In addition, measures have been taken to improve the skills of teachers and production masters working in tourism and hotel management colleges in Turkey and other countries.

MAIN PART

According to a statement issued by the State Committee for Tourism Development of Uzbekistan, from 2018 to 2022 it is planned to build 278 hotels in the country. Most importantly, the construction of these hotels will be modeled on the architecture of hotels in Turkey. It was noted that the construction of these hotels is planned on the basis of a private partnership. The statement said that the construction of 100 hotels in 2018-2020 on the basis of public-private partnership and 178 hotels in 2021-2022 will be completed and put into operation, adding that the experience of hotels in Turkey will be used in the construction of hotels. The construction of the mentioned hotels is also modeled on 80-500-room hotels in Turkey.

The Uzbek government, which wants to use Turkey's experience in the tourism sector, had previously appointed Sadik Badak, a former Turkish lawmaker, as an adviser to Uzbekistan's State Committee for Tourism Development.

In order to provide the tourist complexes and organizations of the national company "Uzbektourism" with qualified specialists who can organize the work of hotels in the Republic of Uzbekistan at the level of world standards, the Cabinet of Ministers decides: "Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan "To establish the Republican Uzbek-Turkish Lyceum of Hospitality and Tourism of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the National Company and the 24th Secondary Vocational School of the Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Turkey in Tashkent. The proposal was accepted.

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to accelerate the development of the tourism industry" dated January 5, 2019 No PP-4095, the Cabinet of Ministers decides:

1. Regulations on the procedure for allocating subsidies to investors for the construction and equipping of new hotels and the allocation of funds from the state budget for partial financing of organizations on the basis of the franchising

agreement were approved in accordance with the Annex.

2. To the state committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on development of tourism together with the interested ministries and departments within a month the regulatory legal acts accepted by them have been brought into accord with this resolution.

3. Control of execution of this resolution to assign to the Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan for social development AA Abdukhakimov and the acting chairman of the State committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on development of tourism AA Akkulov.

In order to develop the hotel industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a lot of work has been done. It is planned to exchange proposals between foreign countries and the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to expect very high results. In order to develop the hotel industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, agreements have been signed with foreign hotels. Hotels that have agreed to this agreement are:

1. The land of legends kingdom hotel
2. Maxx Royal Belek Golf Resort
3. Grand Park Lara Hotel

Fifteen subject teachers of technical colleges and colleges under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports will take part in a training course organized by the Turkish International Cooperation and Development Agency (TIKA) from September 26 to October 11 in Antalya, Turkey.

✔ In a 2-week course, Tourism and Hospitality teachers will have the opportunity to improve their professionalism.

✔ All expenses related to the participants' visit to Turkey will be covered by TIKA

The seminar includes theoretical lessons on catering, occupational safety, guest service, types of services, Turkish tourism development strategies, types and their implementation in Uzbekistan, as well as practical lessons. In addition, practical classes are being held on the example of 5-star hotels in Antalya. Makhroyal won practical training at a 5-star hotel, where guests were given practical skills such as service and room types. In addition, classes on world food and beverages, hotel automation system (check in / check out / booking / reservation ...) are conducted by qualified teachers from 9 am to 4 pm. Members of the training, ie teachers of tourism universities, colleges and technical schools, are actively involved.

Very high results were expected from the contracts and proposals submitted for the development of the hotel industry and tourism. First, a memorandum of cooperation will be signed between the ministries of tourism. Suggestions were made to improve the skills of teachers and masters of industrial education in Turkey and other countries. It should be added that the introduction of production and undergraduate internships abroad for students studying in the field of tourism was also among these proposals. In order to build hotels and provide high-quality education to students, it is also planned to attract high-class experts. The purpose of these proposals was to form a sense of international friendship and solidarity in the development of tourism and hotel industry in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to improve trade relations, to further develop domestic and foreign tourism..

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that in order to develop tourism and hotel industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, many measures have been taken, in particular, a lot of work has been done in cooperation with foreign countries, the Republic of Turkey. agreements that were also beneficial for. Suggestions, decisions, and laws have been made to provide more knowledge, experience, and skills to students majoring in tourism and hotel management.

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